

Action Plan or Faction Plan? Germany's Eclectic Approach to Conflict Prevention

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This is an Author's Accepted Manuscript of an Article published under the same title in International Peacekeeping [copyright Taylor & Francis], 17 (2010): 1, 93-107; the article is available online at <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/13533311003589264>. [doi: 10.1080/13533311003589264]

Keywords: conflict prevention, post-conflict peacebuilding, policy coherence, German action plan, German foreign policy

Abstract: Conflict prevention, more than other fields of international politics and foreign policy, is characterized by a multiplicity of state and non-state actors, giving rise to particularly complex coordination challenges. This article evaluates the extent to which the German response to these challenges, the action plan for civilian conflict prevention, has succeeded in its aim of improving coordination with the ultimate aim to increase policy coherence between different governmental agencies as well as with civil society actors. It finds that although the general approach is indeed promising, the government's lack of commitment prevents it from tapping into the action plan's full potential.

Introduction¹

Successful conflict prevention above all depends on effective coordination. In any peace operation, a plethora of actors, national ministries, international organizations and NGOs is involved. In the mid-1990s, researchers and practitioners became increasingly aware that these actors' efforts can, if incoherent, lead to unintended negative consequences (contravening the 'do no harm' rule),² and that in order to avoid these in conflict-prevention, coordination as the main

¹ A previous version of this paper was presented at the research colloquium of the Institute for Development and Peace (INEF), University of Duisburg-Essen. We would like to thank the participants, in particular Tobias Debiel and Angelika Spelten, for helpful comments. We are furthermore grateful to Christian Reisinger as well as the editor and reviewers of *International Peacekeeping* for providing valuable suggestions.

² Mary B. Anderson, *Do No Harm: How Aid Can Support Peace—or War*, Boulder, CO: Lynne Rienner, 1999.

means by which to increase policy coherence between the different actors is crucially important.

³ Building on this perception, international organizations and national governments have undertaken reforms to facilitate and deepen coordination among actors involved. For instance, since the 1990s the UN has emphasized on so-called ‘integrated missions’ to improve policy coherence among UN agencies and programmes.⁴ Several governments, notably the UK, Sweden and Germany, have developed concepts to facilitate policy coherence through enhanced coordination, including the UK government’s Conflict Prevention Pools (CPPs).⁵ Although the CPPs are considered to be a successful model of inter-ministerial coordination, some commentators argue that the German government has gained a superior model with its action plan – ‘Civilian Crisis Prevention, Conflict Resolution and Post-Conflict Peace-Building’ (henceforth ‘action plan’)^{6,7} Two features distinguish the German action plan from the efforts of other European governments and potentially render it a particularly innovative instrument that could serve as a model for other nations:⁸ an explicit emphasis on the *civilian* component of conflict prevention and a focus not only on inter-ministerial coordination but also on coordination with non-state actors.⁹

This article evaluates the German action plan with respect to its ability to improve policy coherence in the field of civilian conflict prevention. Broadly understood, policy coherence refers to the fact when ‘various policies go together because they share a set of ideas or

³ On the problem of policy coherence in conflict prevention, see e.g. Robert Picciotto, ‘Aid and Conflict: the Policy Coherence Challenge’, *Conflict, Security & Development*, Vol.4, No.3, 2004, pp.543–62.

⁴ See Susanna P. Campbell, ‘(Dis)Integration, Incoherence and Complexity in UN Post-conflict Interventions’, *International Peacekeeping*, Vol.15, No.4, 2008, pp. 556-569.

⁵ See Greg Austin, Emery Brusset, Malcolm Chalmers, and Juliet Pierce, *Evaluation of the Conflict Prevention Pools: Synthesis Report*, London: Department for International Development, 2004, accessed at <http://www.dfid.gov.uk/aboutdfid/performance/files/ev647synthesis.pdf>.

⁶ Federal Government, Action Plan ‘Civilian Crisis Prevention, Conflict Resolution and Post-Conflict Peace-building’, Berlin: Federal Government, 2004.

⁷ See Andreas Mehler and Daniel Dückers’s otherwise critical article, ‘Deutsche Außenpolitik und Krisenprävention: Schicksal eines vordergründig erfolgreichen Paradigmas’ [German Foreign Policy and Crisis Prevention: The Fate of a Seemingly Successful Paradigm], in Thomas Jäger, Alexander Höse and Kai Oppermann (eds.) *Deutsche Außenpolitik: Sicherheit, Wohlfahrt, Institutionen und Normen* [German Foreign Policy: Security, Welfare, Institutions and Norms], Wiesbaden: VS Verlag, 2007, pp.218–40, at p.232.

⁸ Christoph Weller, Zwischen Normen und Reformen: Deutsche Außenpolitik in der Weltgesellschaft [Between Norms and Reforms: German Foreign Policy in World Society], Paper Prepared for the Panel ‘Reform der Außenpolitik’ [Reforms in Foreign Policy] at the 23rd Academic Convention of the German Political Science Association (DVPW), 27 Sept. 2006, in Münster, accessed at <http://www.dvpw.de/dummy/feadmin/docs/2006xWeller.pdf>.

⁹ Tobias Debiel, ‘Wie weiter mit effektiver Krisenprävention? Der Aktionsplan der Bundesregierung im Vergleich zu den britischen Conflict Prevention Pools’ [How to Go on with Effective Crisis Prevention? The Federal Government’s Action Plan in Comparison with the British Conflict Prevention Pools], *Die Friedens-Warte*, Vol.79, No.3-4, 2004, pp. 253-298, at p. 293; Federal Government, *Action Plan*, p. 1.

objectives'.¹⁰ The central means by which different actors achieve or improve policy coherence is coordination, that is, mutual information and consultation among the actors regarding their aims and (planned) policy measures. We limit our analysis to the coordination among domestic actors, which we believe to be a necessary prerequisite for international coordination (and consequently policy coherence) in the field.¹¹ The article first identifies structural problems of civilian conflict prevention. This is followed by a brief presentation of the action plan and the coordination measures introduced by it. Subsequently, the article examines the extent to which it has improved institutionalized coordination (and consequently policy coherence) in the field of civilian conflict prevention, focusing on four areas: (1) early warning and early action, coordination (2) between the different ministries as well as (3) with civil society, and (4) public awareness and financial support. We argue that although the action plan in principle presents a highly innovative approach and a potential model, it falls short of achieving its goal to significantly improve the coherence of German conflict prevention policies. Persistent shortcomings in the coordination between different ministries and with societal organizations remain, mainly of the government's reluctance to fully implement the action plan (and thus tap its full potential).

Civilian Conflict Prevention: Challenges and the Need for Policy Coherence

Conflict prevention can be broadly understood as:

any structural or intercessory means to keep intrastate or interstate tensions and disputes from escalating into significant violence and use of armed force, to strengthen the capabilities of parties to possible violent conflicts for resolving their disputes peacefully, and to progressively reduce the underlying problems that produce those tensions and disputes.¹²

¹⁰ Peter J. May, Joshua Sapotichne and Samuel Workman, 'Policy Coherence and Policy Domains', *Policy Studies Journal*, Vol.34, No.3, 2006, p. 382.

¹¹ Ulrich Schneckener, *International Statebuilding: Dilemmas, Strategies and Challenges for German Foreign Policy*, SWP Research Paper RP 9, October 2007, Berlin: Stiftung Wissenschaft und Politik, 2007, p. 13.

¹² Michael Lund, 'Preventing Violent Intrastate Conflicts: Learning Lessons from Experience', in Paul van Tongeren, Hans van de Veen, and Juliette Verhoeven (eds.) *Searching for Peace in Europe and Eurasia: an Overview of Conflict Prevention and Peacebuilding Activities*, London: Lynne Rienner, 2002, pp. 99-119, at p.117, note 6.

As opposed to the analytical division into conflict prevention (prior to the outbreak of violence), conflict resolution (during an armed conflict) and peace consolidation (after the termination of combat), the understanding of prevention employed here is broader, encompassing ‘different entry points for intervention at the various stages of conflict cycles.’¹³ Nevertheless, it aims to address crises and disputes as soon as possible, at best before they can turn into violent conflict. Apart from avoiding human suffering, the main advantage is that it is much more cost-efficient to address possible conflicts early than to engage in peace enforcement or post-conflict peacebuilding.

It is important to note that in the action plan, the civilian aspect refers to the long-term goal of establishing mechanisms of peaceful management of disputes, not to the actors involved. Thus, armed forces can generally be included in civilian conflict prevention endeavours. A military intervention might, for instance, help to end the fighting. It can, however, only do so for a limited time. Moreover, in the long run, a foreign military presence has a high chance of provoking opposition by local actors and thus could turn out to be counter-productive. It is far from safe to say that military measures are more cost-efficient.¹⁴ Military missions are only of limited value for prevention,¹⁵ and building a lasting peace necessitates long-term civilian measures that the military cannot be a substitute for.¹⁶

However, there are several problems a government faces when engaging in civilian conflict prevention.

The first challenge is the early warning problem. Conflict prevention aims at an intervention as early as possible. While disputes are seen as unavoidable in any given society, it is their escalation into armed violence that conflict prevention seeks to inhibit by addressing the

¹³ Mary Kaldor, Mary Martin and Sabine Selchow, ‘Human Security: a Strategic Narrative for Europe’, *International Affairs*, Vol.83, No.2, 2007, p. 278.

¹⁴ Martina Fischer, ‘Der Aktionsplan Krisenprävention der Bundesregierung – Von der Bestandsaufnahme zur Selbstverpflichtung für eine zivile Außenpolitik?’ [The Federal Government’s Action Plan for Crisis Prevention – From Stock-taking to a Commitment to a Civilian Foreign Policy?], *Die Friedens-Warte*, Vol.79, No.3-4, 2004, p. 320; Michael Brzoska, ‘Sind militärische Interventionen ihr Geld wert? Zur Notwendigkeit und Problematik begleitender Kosten- und Nutzenanalysen’ [Are Military Interventions Worth The Money? On the Necessity and Problematique of Accompanying Cost and Benefit Analyses], in Bruno Schoch, Andreas Heinemann-Grüder, Jochen Hippler, Markus Weingardt and Reinhard Mutz (eds.) *Friedensgutachten 2007 [Peace Report]*, Berlin: LIT Verlag, 2007, p. 84.

¹⁵ Hans J. Gießmann, ‘Bunderwehr zur Prävention?’ [The Bundeswehr as an Instrument for Prevention?], in Hans J. Gießmann and Armin Wagner (eds.) *Armee im Einsatz. Grundlagen, Strategien und Ergebnisse einer Beteiligung der Bundeswehr [An Army Deployed: Basis, Strategies and Results of a Participation of the Bundeswehr]*, Baden-Baden: Nomos, 2009, pp. 46-59.

¹⁶ Jennifer M. Hazen, ‘Can Peacekeepers Be Peacebuilders?’, *International Peacekeeping*, Vol.14, No.3, 2007, pp. 323-338.

underlying causes.¹⁷ In reality, however, in most cases – particularly in regions not subject to regular media attention – actors do not become aware of imminent crises until the violence occurs that should have been prevented in the first place. The problem arising from that task is how to judge whether local mechanisms of (non-violent) conflict resolution are overextended and an external intervention is necessary. This requires the development of indicators other than the outbreak of mass violence. Furthermore, if an intervention is deemed necessary, this information has to be handed on to international actors as soon as possible to ensure that countermeasures can be taken a timely fashion.¹⁸ A dramatic example is the 2004 resurgence of violence in Kosovo, during which (false) media reports about the drowning of three young children that allegedly had been chased into a river by Serbs led to Albanian riots. Despite alerts by representatives of early warning systems like, for instance, the UN Development Programme's 'Early Warning System Kosovo', no steps were taken to prevent a renewed outbreak of violence, simply because the information was not transferred to the decision makers involved.¹⁹ Thus, it is crucial that state actors systematically crosslink not only their separate early-warning systems but that they also institutionalize regular information exchange with non-state actors who often have more information on grievances giving rise to violence and can help raise awareness for the need to act.²⁰ Only if decision makers become aware of alerts issued by other ministries as well as NGOs and research institutes, can early warning translate into effective foreign policy action.

Another closely related challenge is the problem of root cause analysis. Current conflicts within states involve a variety of state and non-state actors with a complex mixture of economic,

¹⁷ Christoph Weller, 'Zivile Konfliktbearbeitung im Aufwind? Regierung und Nichtregierungsorganisationen formulieren ehrgeizige Pläne' [Civilian Conflict Management on the Rise? Government and Non-governmental Organisations formulate Ambitious Plans], in Christoph Weller, Ulrich Ratsch, Reinhard Mutz, Bruno Schoch, and Corinna Hauswedell (eds.) *Friedensgutachten 2004*, Münster: Lit, 2004, pp. 279-288, at p. 279.

¹⁸ Angelika Spelten, 'Was hat Frühwarnung mit der Vermeidung von Krieg zu tun?' [What Is the Connection Between Early Warning and the Prevention of Wars?], in Christoph Weller, Ulrich Ratsch, Reinhard Mutz, Bruno Schoch, and Corinna Hauswedell (eds.) *Friedensgutachten 2004*, Münster: Lit, 2004, pp. 269-278, at pp. 269-270.

¹⁹ Tanja Rother, 'Early warning und early action: Potenziale nicht-staatlicher Akteure der zivilen Konfliktbearbeitung' [Early Warning and Early Action: The Potential of Non-state Actors of Civilian Conflict Management], in Hans J. Gießmann and Patricia Schneider (eds.) *Reformen zur Friedenskonsolidierung: Forschungen im akademischen Netzwerk Südosteuropa 2004 / 2005 [Reforms to Consolidate Peace: Research of the Academic Network Southeast Europe 2004/2005]*, Hamburger Beiträge zur Friedensforschung und Sicherheitspolitik 144, Hamburg: Institut für Friedensforschung und Sicherheitspolitik an der Universität Hamburg, 2006, pp. 31-61.

²⁰ Carnegie Commission on Preventing Deadly Conflict, *Preventing Deadly Conflict: Final Report*, New York: Carnegie Corporation, 1997, p. 113.

political, identity-based and ethnic motives.²¹ Factors like state failure, war economies and protracted refugee situations, often connected to long-winded intrastate conflicts, render the latter even more difficult to end and prone to cross-border escalation.²² Furthermore, the complex mixture of actors and motives seriously hampers an identification of the problems to address and the actions relevant to achieve a lasting peace. Identification of root causes, and relevant actors, of a conflict is crucial, since addressing these issues is the only way to avoid the continued opposition of peace spoilers and a renewed outbreak of violence. This is particularly difficult for a foreign (and thus distantly-located) government and also requires close coordination with other actors such as developmental organizations, NGOs, local grassroots initiatives and so on that work to facilitate peace. NGOs are often the sole actors already on-site, working to address the underlying causes of conflict, for example through mediation, network-building and grassroots peace initiatives.²³ Particularly local NGOs have ‘deep knowledge of regional and local issues, cultures, and relationships’,²⁴ which is indispensable for any serious conflict prevention effort.

Closely related to this hitch is another challenge, the problem of contradictory policy goals. This refers to the fact that conflict prevention policies (and indeed cultures)²⁵ often clash with policies in other areas of foreign policy, which can lead to a situation in which different ministries within a government pursue even contradictory policies and thus hamper each other’s efforts.²⁶ This problem is aggravated when it comes to dealing with non-governmental actors.²⁷

²¹ Martin van Creveld, *The Transformation of War: the Most Radical Reinterpretation of Armed Conflict since Clausewitz*, New York: Free Press, 1991; Mary Kaldor, *New and Old Wars: Organized Violence in a Global Era*, Cambridge: Polity, 1999; Herfried Münkler, *The New Wars*, Cambridge: Polity, 2005.

²² Charles King, *Ending Civil Wars*, Adelphi Paper 308, Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1997, pp. 29-53; Robert I. Rotberg, ‘The New Nature of Nation-State Failure’, *The Washington Quarterly*, Vol.25, No.3, 2002, pp. 85-96; François Jean and Jean-Christophe Rufin, eds., *Economie des guerres civiles [The Economy of Civil Wars]*, Paris: Hachette, 1996; William Reno, *Warlord Politics and African States*, London: Lynne Rienner, 1999; Gil Loescher and James Milner, ‘The Long Road Home: Protracted Refugee Situations in Africa’, *Survival*, Vol.47, No.2, 2005, pp. 153-174; Robert B. Zoellick, ‘Fragile States: Securing Development’, *Survival*, Vol.50, No.6, 2008, pp. 67 - 84.

²³ Tobias Debiel and Monika Sticht, *Towards a New Profile? Development, Humanitarian and Conflict-Resolution NGOs in the Age of Globalization*, INEF Report 79, Institute for Development and Peace, 2005, p. 27-37.

²⁴ Carnegie Commission, *Preventing Deadly Conflict*, p. 113.

²⁵ Robert A. Rubinstein, Diana M. Keller and Michael E. Scherger, ‘Culture and Interoperability in Integrated Missions’, *International Peacekeeping*, Vol.15, No.4, 2008, pp. 540-555.

²⁶ See e.g. Tom Porteous, ‘British government policy in sub-Saharan Africa under New Labour’, *International Affairs*, Vol.81, No.2, 2004, pp. 281-297.

²⁷ See, for example, Debiel and Sticht, *Towards a New Profile*, pp. 35-37; Karen Ballentine and Heiko Nitzschke, ‘Business and Armed Conflict: an Assessment of Issues and Options’, *Die Friedens-Warte*, Vol.79, No.1-2, 2004, pp. 35-56.

In addressing challenges that civilian conflict prevention faces, close coordination between the different actors involved is a key issue. For any measures to be successful, a plethora of governmental and non-governmental, international, regional, national and local actors have to cooperate if only to achieve a remotely coherent strategy and to avoid that the measures taken by one actor jeopardize the success of another actor's initiatives.

In addition to the coordination problems addressed above, civilian conflict prevention faces the problem of policy mediation. One crucial prerequisite of any policy is the question of public awareness. All actors – in particular governmental actors – involved in any policy issue depend on legitimacy. Only if the populace deems policy measures legitimate, can the necessary financial and personnel resources be mobilized. In the field of conflict prevention this is particularly complicated, for the public usually becomes aware of the need for civilian conflict prevention only through media reports on the very armed conflicts that are supposed to be prevented in the first place. Success in civilian conflict prevention is only indicated by the absence of anything measurable, namely, the outbreak of violence. Thus, it is particularly difficult to judge if the intervention was necessary in the first place, that is, if an outbreak of violence would have taken place without it.²⁸ Due to the 'invisibility' of its successes, civilian conflict prevention depends on an active communication and lobbying strategy that raises awareness in the populace and to justify the need for steady and increased funding.²⁹

Addressing the Challenges: The German Action Plan

After the 1998 Bundestag elections, the newly formed coalition government of the Social Democratic (SPD) and the Green parties, took up elements from an extensive debate in the academic discipline of peace research³⁰ as well as in public forums, and in 2000 adopted the 'Comprehensive Concept of the Federal Government on Civilian Crisis Prevention, Conflict

²⁸ Volker Matthies, *Krisenprävention: Vorbeugen ist besser als heilen* [Crisis Prevention: Prophylaxis Is Better than Cure], Opladen: Leske + Budrich, 2000, pp.111-124.

²⁹ Christoph Weller, *Aktionsplan Zivile Krisenprävention der Bundesregierung – Jetzt ist dynamische Umsetzung gefordert* [The Action Plan Civilian Crisis Prevention – It Is Time for Dynamic Implementation], INEF Policy Brief 2/2007, Duisburg: Institute for Development and Peace, 2007, p. 4.

³⁰ See Andreas Buro, 'Weichenstellung ziviler Konfliktbearbeitung in Europa' [Turning the Switchblade for Civilian Conflict Management in Europe], in Wolfgang R. Vogt (ed.) *Frieden als Zivilisierungsprojekt* [Peace as a Civilizing Project], Baden-Baden: Nomos, 1995, pp. 73-82; Jörg Calließ, 'Friede kann nicht erzwungen werden: Plädoyer für zivile Konfliktbearbeitung' [Peace Cannot be Enforced: Plea for a Civilian Conflict Management], *Berliner Debatte/Initial*, No. 6/2005, pp. 37-46.

Resolution and Post-Conflict Peace-Building’ (henceforth comprehensive concept).³¹ This stated the national principles of, and possibilities for, civilian conflict prevention building on an ‘extended security concept that embraces political, economic, ecological and social stability’, in turn based on the ‘respect for human rights, social justice, the rule of law, participatory decision-making, the protection of natural resources, development opportunities in all regions of the world and the use of peaceful conflict resolution mechanisms’.³² Needless to say, such a broad approach does not translate easily into a coherent policy or coordinated measures. From an initiative of individual Green Party MPs, the action plan was developed to concretize the principles of the comprehensive concept.³³ It was compiled under the auspices of the foreign ministry, in close cooperation with experts from different ministries, academic advisers and members of civil society organizations, and it incorporated insights from a report taking stock of civil society approaches in conflict management.³⁴

Overall, the topics addressed in the action plan included not only the ‘classical’ areas of foreign policy, but also policy areas that lie within the responsibilities of other ministries, for example, development policy, environmental issues and defence. As the action plan points out, ‘[t]he aim of introducing crisis prevention as a cross-sectoral task is to develop methods, instruments and procedures to ensure that due attention is accorded to crisis prevention in all stages and sectors of government activity’.³⁵ It aspires to be the ‘binding frame of reference’ for the different ministries’ crisis prevention policies.³⁶ To facilitate policy coherence in the activities of the different state and non-state actors involved, however, the plan is not confined to a list of priorities for crisis prevention, but also introduces a number of institutional innovations.

³¹ Federal Government, *Comprehensive Concept of the Federal Government on Civilian Crisis Prevention, Conflict Resolution and Post-Conflict Peace-Building*, accessed at www.auswaertiges-amt.de/www/en/aussenpolitik/friedenspolitik/ziv_km/konfliktpraev_html.

³² Federal Government, *Comprehensive Concept*.

³³ Weller, ‘Zivile Konfliktbearbeitung im Aufwind’.

³⁴ Plattform Zivile Konfliktbearbeitung, *Frieden braucht Gesellschaft! Gesellschaftliche Ansätze in der Zivilen Konfliktbearbeitung. Eine Bestandsaufnahme [No Peace Without Society! Societal Approaches in Civilian Conflict Management: Taking Stock]*, Wahlenau: Plattform Zivile Konfliktbearbeitung, 2003, accessed at http://www.ifa.de/zivik/download/frieden_20041116.pdf.

³⁵ Federal Government, *Action plan*, p. 87.

³⁶ Federal Government, ‘Working Together to Strengthen Security and Stability through Crisis Prevention’: 1st Federal Government Report on the Implementation of the Action Plan ‘Civilian Crisis Prevention, Conflict Resolution and Post-Conflict Peacebuilding’, Berlin: Federal Government, 2006, p. 93, accessed at <http://www.auswaertiges-amt.de/diplo/de/Aussenpolitik/FriedenSicherheit/Krisenpraevention/Aktionsplan1Bericht0506-EN.pdf>.

Within each ministry, some heads of units or departments have been appointed as crisis prevention commissioners or representatives.³⁷ To improve and systematize coordination, the Federal Foreign Office has been assigned the overall task of coordinating the different ministerial activities in the field of civilian conflict prevention. This is reflected in the position of a Commissioner for Civilian Crisis Prevention in the Foreign Office with the rank of ambassador, which was established through the action plan. Most importantly, the action plan created a new coordination committee, the Interministerial Steering Group (ISG), comprising the different ministries' commissioners/representatives and chaired by the Foreign Office's Commissioner for Civilian Crisis Prevention. It has the overall task of implementing and monitoring the action plan. The members of the ISG meet on a regular basis to discuss certain issues and overall to keep each other informed.

To strengthen the integration of non-state actors into the policy process, the Federal Government created an Advisory Board for Civilian Crisis Prevention 'which will provide specialized back-up support for the work of the Interministerial Steering Group'.³⁸ It comprises 19 representatives of civil society groups and umbrella organizations as well as individuals with expert knowledge in the field of conflict prevention who meet twice a year. These include representatives from research institutes, NGO umbrella organizations, and business companies (such as Siemens, BASF, Deutsche Bank), as well as one of each church and political foundation. Furthermore, the Federal Government was committed to submit a report to the German Bundestag every two years, sketching progress in the implementation of the action plan. In May 2006 and July 2008, respectively, the first and second interim reports were issued.³⁹

A Blueprint for a Coherent Foreign Policy?

Half a decade after the adoption of the action plan by the Federal Cabinet, it has now become possible to evaluate the progress achieved in the coordination of Germany's conflict prevention policy. In the first section, we briefly outlined the core problems of civilian conflict prevention

³⁷ Christoph Weller, 'Zivile Krisenprävention und Konfliktbearbeitung: Politische Herausforderungen und der Aktionsplan der Bundesregierung' [Civilian Crisis Prevention and Conflict Management: Political Challenges and the Federal Government's Action Plan], in Renate Grasse, Wilhelm Nolte, and Peter Schlotter (eds.) *Berliner Friedenspolitik? Militärische Transformation - zivile Impulse - europäische Einbindung* [Berlin Peace Policy? Military transformation – Civilian Impetuses – European Embeddedness], Baden-Baden: Nomos, 2008.

³⁸ Federal Government, *Action Plan*, p. 98.

³⁹ Federal Government, 'Working together'; Federal Government, Crisis Prevention as a Shared Task: 2nd Federal Government Report on the Implementation of the Action Plan "Civilian Crisis Prevention, Conflict resolution and Post-Conflict Peacebuilding", Berlin: Federal Foreign Office, 2008, accessed at <http://www.auswaertiges-amt.de/diplo/de/Aussenpolitik/Themen/Krisenpraevention/neu/Downloads/Aktionsplan-Bericht2-en.pdf>.

policies. From this analysis we develop four core criteria to evaluate the plan: (1) early warning and early action; (2) inter-ministerial coordination; (3) coordination with civil society actors; and (4) public awareness and financial support. The first and fourth criteria more or less directly refer to the corresponding problems identified in the first section. The second and third criteria (coordination between different ministries and state agencies as well as with civil society) have been chosen here because the challenge of policy coherence could only be met with better coordination mechanisms. Achieving early warning and action, a thorough root cause analysis, and balancing contradictory policy goals all depend on coordination among the different actors involved.

Early Warning and Early Action

As noted argued above, a systematic analysis of conflict potential in the country or region concerned is a crucial precondition for any effective conflict prevention. However, there is still much confusion over the use of conflict types and indicators among the different actors involved in German conflict prevention policy, raising doubts as to the ‘effectiveness or existence of an overall analytical framework’.⁴⁰ Although different departments (the Federal Foreign Office, Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development [*Bundesministerium für wirtschaftliche Zusammenarbeit und Entwicklung* – BMZ], Federal Ministry of Defence and the intelligence services) produce early warning analyses, there is no systematic attempt to cross-link information and different assessments.⁴¹ This unfortunate situation is not due to a general unavailability of established early-warning instruments. The BMZ for instance has relied on a fairly successful early warning instrument for years, which could relatively easily have been applied on an inter-ministerial level.⁴² With respect to early warning, the only progress

⁴⁰ Andreas Mehler and Hans-Chrsitian Mahnke, Major flaws in conflict prevention policies towards Africa. The conceptual deficits of international actors’ approaches and how to overcome them, Working Papers Global and Area Studies 4, Hamburg: German Overseas Institute, 2005, p. 28, accessed at http://www.giga-hamburg.de/dl/download.php?d=/content/publikationen/pdf/wp04_mehler.pdf.

⁴¹ Christoph Weller, ‘Jetzt ist dynamische Umsetzung gefordert’ [It Is Time for a Dynamic Implementation], *Frieden braucht Fachleute*, No.3/2007, p. 3; Federal Government, *Antwort der Bundesregierung auf die Kleine Anfrage der Abgeordneten Winfried Nachtwei, Kerstin Müller (Köln), Ute Koczy, weiterer Abgeordneter und der Fraktion Bündnis 90/Die Grünen* (elektronische Vorab-Fassung) [Response of the Federal Government to a Minor Request by the Members of Parliament Winfried Nachtwei, Kerstin Müller (Köln), Ute Koczy, additional members of parliament and the faction of Bündnis 90/Die Grünen], Drucksache 16/9363, Berlin: Deutscher Bundestag, 2008, p. 13, accessed at <http://dip21.bundestag.de/dip21/btd/16/093/1609363.pdf>.

⁴² The BMZ’s early-warning system consists of a number of indicators to assess the crisis potential in specific societies. On the basis of these indicators, each year country experts measure the crisis level in these countries. The focus here however is limited to those countries that are partners of German development policy. For a more detailed examination of different early warning systems, see Spelten, ‘Was hat Frühwarnung’.

mentioned in the 2006 interim report is the creation of a working group within the defence ministry focusing on crisis developments relevant to defence policy,⁴³ and the second report concentrates on international cooperation in this regard. If different governmental actors cannot even bring together their various assessments in early warning, coherent action with civil society organizations – not to speak of international actors – becomes virtually impossible. The only positive example for inter-ministerial cooperation as well as that with civil society in the field of early warning is provided by the country-specific discussion groups, which are anchored in the action plan and subordinated to the steering group, working to develop strategies for specific regions in close coordination with civil society. A pilot project on Nigeria, however, received a negative evaluation due to a lack of conceptual clarity, insufficient personnel resources as well as a lack of incentives for the ministries to achieve policy coherence.⁴⁴

Inter-ministerial Coordination

Enhanced inter-ministerial coordination looms large in the action plan, and although the first interim report emphasizes the ‘considerable progress’ of the first two years, in particular with respect to ‘greater coherence and coordination’,⁴⁵ it also points to infrastructural deficits that have become evident and calls for the strengthening of the national infrastructure to be made a priority task for the 2006–08 period. In their 2005 coalition agreement, the Christian Democratic Union (CDU), the Christian Social Union of Bavaria (CSU) and the SPD committed themselves to implement the action plan and, more specifically, to strengthen the steering group.⁴⁶ Although the latter’s setup presents an important step towards a further integrated approach to conflict prevention, after almost six years, significant shortcomings prevail. The central weakness of the ISG is that its role still remains limited to horizontal coordination and information. The steering group cannot take the initiative without an assignment by a ministry’s leadership. A real improvement in terms of policy coherence, however, would require the ISG to become a supervisory body, closely linked to the state secretary level and equipped with an independent

⁴³ Weller, *Aktionsplan Zivile Krisenprävention*, p. 9.

⁴⁴ Daniel Dücker, *Pilotprojekt ‘Gesprächskreis Nigeria’ der deutschen Bundesregierung: Ein Ansatz der inklusiven Politikentwicklung im Rahmen der zivilen Krisenprävention* [The Federal Government’s Pilot Project ‘Roundtable Nigeria’: An Approach to the Inclusive Policy Development in the Field of Civilian Crisis Prevention], Stuttgart: Institut für Auslandsbeziehungen, 2005.

⁴⁵ Federal Government, *Working Together*, p. 67.

⁴⁶ CDU, CSU and SPD, *Working Together for Germany – with Courage and Compassion: Coalition Agreement between the CDU, CSU and SPD*, Berlin: Press and Information Office of the Federal Government, 2005, p. 131, accessed at http://www.spd.de/show/1683399/Koalitionsvertrag2005_engl.pdf.

pool of financial and personnel resources to develop initiatives on its own as well as prevention concepts for crisis regions, to systematically evaluate conflict prevention policies.⁴⁷ Despite the first interim report's emphasis on the necessity of strengthening the steering group, this is not matched in practice. Instead, the second report merely reifies the ISG's character as a non-hierarchical body to facilitate horizontal coordination and information sharing.⁴⁸ Arguably, the ISG is further weakened by the fact that the tasks of the Commissioner for Civilian Crisis Prevention in the Foreign Office have now been assigned to the Commissioner for Global Issues. Although the latter is higher in rank and has more resources at his/her disposal, conflict prevention will only be one of several issues (such as poverty reduction, human rights and international terrorism) s/he has to deal with. Whether this will prove to be a positive change or lead to the marginalization of conflict prevention remains to be seen. Despite the remaining deficits, the 2008 report asserts that civilian conflict prevention 'is now accepted as being an inter-ministerial, inter-departmental and cross-sectoral task' and that the structures that have been created with the action plan have 'proved themselves'.⁴⁹

The steering group stands in stark contrast to the UK's conflict prevention pools, which are jointly administered by the Foreign and Commonwealth Office, the Ministry of Defence and the Department for International Development. Nevertheless, the possibility of establishing a jointly-administered prevention pool along the lines of the CPPs was rejected after evaluation due to 'considerable differences between the organization of the executive power, the provisions of budgetary law, and political and financial conditions' in the two countries.⁵⁰

Furthermore, the promised integration of Germany's peace and security policies is not even carried through in the central government documents. For instance, the action plan and the 'White Paper 2006 on German Security Policy and the Future of the Bundeswehr' have been developed largely detached from each other.⁵¹ Instead of integrating the two documents, the

⁴⁷ Peter Croll, Tobias Debiel and Stephan Klingebiel, Plädoyer für eine integrative deutsche Sicherheitsstrategie: Warum die Bundesregierung sich im europäischen Kontext mit zivilen Akzenten in der Sicherheitsstrategie stärker profilieren sollte [Plea for an Integrative German Security Strategy: Why the Federal Government Should Distinguish Itself in the European Context by Focusing on Civilian Aspects], Bonn: Bonn International Center for Conversion, 2007, accessed at <http://www.bicc.de/publications/other/diskussionspapier.pdf>;

Weller, Aktionsplan Zivile Krisenprävention.

⁴⁸ Federal Government, *Crisis Prevention*, p. 78.

⁴⁹ Federal Government, *Crisis Prevention*, pp. 15, 8.

⁵⁰ Federal Government, *Working Together*, p. 83.

⁵¹ Federal Ministry of Defence, *White Paper 2006 on German Security Policy and the Future of the Bundeswehr*, Berlin: Federal Ministry of Defence, 2006, accessed at http://www.bmvg.de/portal/PA_1_0_P3/PortalFiles/C1256EF40036B05B/W26UWAMT995INFODE/W+2006+eng+DS.pdf?yw_repository=youtatweb.

action plan is only dealt with as an ‘example’ of inter-ministerial security policy in the White Paper,⁵² and the comprehensive concept seen as one of the ‘components’ of German security policy.⁵³ The small weight attributed to the action plan in the White Paper indeed indicates how far away the German government still is from establishing civilian conflict prevention as a cross-sectoral task and ensuring ‘that due attention is accorded to crisis prevention in all stages and sectors of government activity’, as the action plan heralds.⁵⁴

In particular civil–military cooperation proves difficult due to the defence ministry’s departmental interests. As the defence White Paper reveals, the defence ministry increasingly aims to establish itself as a conflict prevention actor.⁵⁵ But to date the development of the necessary general concepts of civil–military cooperation remains fragmentary and mainly takes place at the tactical level.⁵⁶ One well-known example is the Provincial Reconstruction Teams in Afghanistan. These teams, which comprise members of the armed forces as well as representatives of the Foreign Office and the BMZ, work to strengthen the central government’s influence in the local provinces, to foster civil reconstruction, information gathering and the provision of security. However, thus far, military and development policy goals have not been successfully combined. A lack of resource pooling as well as the tendency to perceive other ministries or agencies as competitors rather than as partners have proven to be significant obstacles for effective cooperation.⁵⁷ For the *Bundeswehr*, development policy still is seen mainly as a tool to increase acceptance among the local populace for the military presence, whereas development cooperation actors point to the importance of sustainability and participation.⁵⁸

⁵² Federal Ministry of Defence, *White Paper 2006*, p. 23.

⁵³ Federal Ministry of Defence, *White Paper 2006*, p. 7.

⁵⁴ Federal Government, *Action Plan*, p. 87.

⁵⁵ On the changing role of armed forces in Europe more generally, see Timothy Edmunds, ‘What *Are* Armed Forces for? The Changing Nature of Military Forces in Europe’, *International Affairs*, Vol.82, No.6, 2006, pp. 1059-1075.

⁵⁶ Jochen Hippler, ‘Bedingungen, Kriterien und Grenzen militärischer Interventionen’ [Conditions, Criteria and Limits of Military Interventions], in Bruno Schoch, Andreas Heinemann-Grüder, Jochen Hippler, Markus Weingardt and Reinhard Mutz (eds.) *Friedensgutachten 2007*, Berlin: LIT Verlag, 2007, p. 117.

⁵⁷ Birgit Hofmann, ‘Identitätskonflikte als Hindernis entwicklungspolitisch-militärischer Zusammenarbeit: das deutsche Engagement im PRT Kunduz aus sozialkonstruktivistischer Perspektive’ [Identity Conflicts as an Obstacle to Cooperation Between Military and Development Actors: German Activities in the PRT Kunduz from a Constructivist Point of View], in Christoph Weller (ed.) *Zivile Konfliktbearbeitung: Aktuelle Forschungsergebnisse [Civilian Conflict Management: New Research Findings]*, INEF Report 85/2007, Duisburg: Institute for Development and Peace, 2007, pp. 61-68.

⁵⁸ Rainer Glassner and Conrad Schetter, ‘Der deutsche Beitrag zum Wiederaufbau Afghanistans seit 2001: Bundeswehreinsatz und ziviles Engagement’ [The German Contribution to Afghan Reconstruction since 2001: Military Mission and Civilian Efforts], in Bruno Schoch, Andreas Heinemann-Grüder, Jochen Hippler, Markus Weingardt and Reinhard Mutz (eds.) *Friedensgutachten 2007*, Berlin: LIT Verlag, 2007, pp. 63-74.

In this regard, conceptual coherence as well as institutional coordination mechanisms has to be improved. The 2004 joint *Utstein* study found Germany lacking in this regard,⁵⁹ and other critics also point to the fact that different German ministries still draw on diverging conceptions of the core problems at hand.⁶⁰ However, only when the central actors involved can agree on the concepts, goals and principles of civilian conflict prevention, can departmental ‘turf wars’ be avoided.⁶¹ In this respect, the steering group could prove to be an important forum for discussion. Overall, however, the German commitment to enhanced interagency cooperation has not gone far in comparison to other governments.⁶²

Coordination with Civil Society Actors

But not only is inter-ministerial coordination still lacking. Another crucial aspect is coordination with civil society. Increased coordination in this regard is desirable for several reasons. First, all conflict prevention actors could benefit from a shared assessment of a situation. State and non-state actors have different sources of information and assessment standards. NGOs are often embedded in the ‘target society’, as they have often been working among local people prior to government activities. Thus, their assessments are more likely to reflect the actual local conditions, and their cooperation is crucial to identify potential local partners. Furthermore, area studies experts and peace researchers can significantly contribute to early warning and the development of appropriate strategies. Private business can also play a role, for instance, by lobbying for peace processes. Thus, regular exchange is crucial for coherent approaches to conflict prevention.⁶³

According to the action plan, coordination with civil society is supposed to take place mainly via the advisory board. Taking into account the heterogeneity of this body and its infrequent meetings, however, the exact form in which advice is supposed to take place remains unclear. Thus, some observers have argued that the advisory board merely fulfils an ‘alibi

⁵⁹ Dan Smith, *Towards a Strategic Framework for Peacebuilding: Getting Their Act Together: Overview report of the Joint Utstein Study of Peacebuilding, Evaluation Report 1/2004*, Oslo: The Royal Norwegian Ministry of Foreign Affairs, 2004, p. 30, accessed at http://www.prio.no/files/file44563_rapport_1.04_webutgave.pdf.

⁶⁰ Mehler and Dücker, ‘Deutsche Außenpolitik’, p. 232.

⁶¹ Kaldor et al., ‘Human Security’, p. 287.

⁶² Schneckener, *International Statebuilding*, p. 24.

⁶³ Tobias Debiel and Angelika Spelten, ‘Krisenprävention und Friedensförderung in der deutschen Entwicklungspolitik’ [Crisis Prevention and the Facilitation of Peace in German Development Policy], in Reinhard Mutz, Bruno Schoch, Corinna Hauswedell, Jochen Hippler and Ulrich Ratsch (eds.) *Friedensgutachten 2006*, Münster: LIT Verlag, 2006, p. 116.

function.’⁶⁴ The second interim report also pleads for closer cooperation between the steering group and the board.⁶⁵ The action plan only rather vaguely announces that individual ministries will ‘where appropriate, hold regular consultations of a general nature or on specific topics or countries’ to facilitate coordination with non-state actors.⁶⁶ Most of the concrete initiatives taken to facilitate exchange with civil society remain those of individual ministries instead of the overall government. The most notable example is the Working Group on Development and Peace (FriEnt), which on the basis of close relations between the BMZ and civil society actors, was developed prior to the action plan. FriEnt comprises seven state and non-state organizations of development cooperation and serves as a platform for information sharing, contributes to the networking of the actors and provides consulting services through research and analysis.⁶⁷

Policy Prerequisites: Public Awareness and Financial Support

Taking into account the structural invisibility of civilian conflict prevention, actively raising public awareness is a crucial precondition for ensuring steady funding. In this regard, the Federal Government’s efforts seem rather disappointing. When the action plan was issued, the government missed the opportunity to seize the opportunity to actively lobby for the utility of civilian conflict prevention. The lack of public awareness can be neatly illustrated by the parliamentary debate on the first interim report. Scheduled for 15 December 2006 (the last session before Christmas), only one state secretary and fewer than 30 MPs stayed for the debate. If the presence of parliamentarians in plenary debates are any indicator for the importance of a particular policy issue, civilian conflict prevention has to be regarded as a mere niche component of German foreign policy.⁶⁸ In the light of the limited awareness the first interim report received in the Bundestag, it is unsurprising that it received almost no media attention. This is even troubling, as a public debate could give civilian conflict prevention the public legitimacy it needs to ensure constant and increased financial and personnel resources.⁶⁹

⁶⁴ Andreas Heinemann-Grüder, ‘Konfliktprävention – eine Alternative zu Militäreinsätzen?’ [Conflict Prevention – an Alternative to Military Operations?], in Bruno Schoch, Andreas Heinemann-Grüder, Jochen Hippler, Markus Weingardt and Reinhard Mutz (eds.) *Friedensgutachten 2007*, Berlin: LIT Verlag, 2007, p. 132.

⁶⁵ Federal Government, *Crisis Prevention*, p. 83.

⁶⁶ Federal Government, *Action Plan*, p. 95.

⁶⁷ FriEnt does, however, only focus on a limited number of countries.

⁶⁸ Weller, *Aktionsplan Zivile Krisenprävention*, p. 7.

⁶⁹ Schneckener, *International Statebuilding*, p. 14.

Thus, in the 2006 report, the Federal Government identifies the absence of a ‘prevention lobby’ as a central problem and commits itself to ‘redouble its efforts to raise the profile of Germany’s contribution to crisis prevention, conflict resolution and post-conflict peace building to a broad interested public by maintaining contact with selected media representatives and keeping them strategically informed, and by holding informative events’.⁷⁰ Whereas enhanced communication was identified as a priority task by the first report, in the 2008 report the communication strategy called for by the advisory board was merely mentioned as ‘one approach’,⁷¹ and with their quite extensive wordage, the reports themselves hardly seemed fit to raise awareness.⁷² No short version of either report was produced, which would make it much easier for the media or interested public to pick up the issue. Moreover, both were published solely on the foreign office’s website; nor was their publication accompanied by a marketing campaign. By contrast, the active promotion and broad attention given to the Defence White Paper clearly shows that the Federal Government is indeed able to raise public attention for those policy issues it deems important. Thus far, however, it has missed the chance to do so with respect to civilian conflict prevention, and the fact that the second interim report has been handled along the lines of the first does not raise hopes that the government is willing to push for enhanced public awareness.⁷³ Furthermore, an initial idea to create a special representative of the Federal Government for civilian conflict prevention, which might raise public awareness,⁷⁴ has been dropped.

One central obstacle, following from the lack of public awareness, remains the problematic financial status of civilian conflict prevention. Already when the action plan was adopted in 2004, the government lacked the will to dedicate additional budgetary resources to civilian conflict prevention, proclaiming instead that it would be ‘working to ensure permanent funding for crisis prevention.’⁷⁵ Nor did the 2006 report link its plea for improved coordination with the intention to increase financial resources.

⁷⁰ Federal Government, *Working Together*, p. 101.

⁷¹ Federal Government, *Crisis Prevention*, p. 16.

⁷² With a length of almost 130 pages, the first report comprises not only a description of the activities undertaken since 2004 but also identifies future priorities. Despite its length of still almost 100 pages, the second interim report simply lists the measures undertaken during the period under review. Future policy priorities play only a minor role, which not only provides an obstacle for an assessment of the activities undertaken after 2008 but also raises doubts as to government’s long-term commitment to civilian conflict prevention.

⁷³ See Frank A. Stengel and Christoph Weller, Vier Jahre Aktionsplan “Zivile Krisenprävention” – war das alles? [Four Years Action Plan “Civilian Crisis Prevention” – Is That It?] GIGA Focus Global 11/2008, Hamburg: GIGA German Institute of Global and Area Studies, 2008.

⁷⁴ Croll, Debiel and Klingebiel, *Plädoyer*.

⁷⁵ Federal Government, *Action Plan*, p. 91.

At first glance, this changed subsequently in 2008 when financial resources committed to tasks, which in principle could be subsumed under the heading of conflict prevention, were increased significantly. The Foreign Office's budgetary item for conflict prevention and resolution was extended from 12 to 60 million euros, including 25 million for a newly-created crisis fund to allow for quick financial contributions to, for instance, UN peacekeeping missions. Furthermore, the BMZ's budget was extended by 14 per cent (to 640 million euros) in 2008. In the years 2005 to 2007, one third, or roughly 1.7 billion euros of development aid was spent in conflict regions, and 700 million related to conflict prevention.⁷⁶ Although the government's equation of development aid with conflict prevention neglects the complex nexus between poverty reduction and conflict prevention, these budget increases are in principle laudable. There are, however, no efforts for true resource pooling to produce financial incentives for coordinated inter-ministerial action in the field of conflict prevention. Almost six years after the inception of the action plan, German conflict prevention policy remains a field of inter-ministerial competition rather than that of a coordinated and coherent policy.

Conclusion

With the action plan, the German Federal Government had taken significant steps to address the complex coordination challenges in the field of civilian conflict prevention. In particular the focus on the civilian aspects of conflict prevention and the coordination with civil society actors renders the action plan a potential model for other countries in tackling the field's coordination challenges. Newly-created institutions like the steering group and the advisory board have significant potential to improve policy coherence.

This article has focused on four key prerequisites of an effective conflict prevention policy (early warning, inter-ministerial coordination, coordination with civil society actors, and public awareness and financial resources) to assess the extent to which the action plan has indeed facilitated foreign policy coherence. Despite the generally laudable initiative of the action plan, however, the Federal Government 'still lacks to meet its own claim in terms of practical and conceptual implementation.'⁷⁷ This is particularly obvious in the field of early warning, where not even the governmental actors have systematically interlinked their instruments, let alone with those of non-state and international actors. Also, more generally, inter-ministerial coordination

⁷⁶ Federal Government, *Crisis Prevention*, p. 84, 85.

⁷⁷ Mehler and Mahnke, *Major Flaws*, p. 25.

remains insufficient. Despite repeated contrary assertions, the steering group has not been strengthened, let alone provided with any steering capacity, and it still suffers from a significant lack of personnel and financial resources that significantly limits its ability to facilitate coordination. As the ISG is not endowed with steering rights, it remains little more than a talking shop. Nor does the advisory board in its current form provide a sufficient forum for regular exchange with civil society actors, mainly because of its infrequent meetings and lack of resources. Although more overall resources have been devoted to conflict-prevention related tasks during the past few years, resource pooling is still lacking. Furthermore, the Federal Government remains reluctant to actively lobby for public awareness for civilian conflict prevention. Without a widespread public understanding of the benefits of civilian conflict prevention, it is doubtful whether funding can be ensured in the long run.

A consequence of the general lack of efficient coordination (in particular in the field of early warning) is that Germany's conflict prevention policies still remain largely reactive in nature. The absence of forceful implementation of the bureaucratic reforms thus continues to undermine the credibility of the offices involved.⁷⁸ Overall, it not only remains unclear whether the Federal Government will be able to meet the complex coordination challenges in this field of foreign policy but also whether civilian conflict prevention can establish itself as a constant feature of German foreign policy. A continued commitment to civilian conflict prevention is put even more into doubt by the fact that it very much depends on the will of the coalition in power, with elections taking place every four years.⁷⁹ While it is too early to provide a substantial assessment of the policy priorities of the new coalition government established in 2009 between CDU, CSU and the Free Democratic Party (FDP), the fact that the action plan is not mentioned once in the coalition agreement might indicate a further shift away from civilian conflict prevention.⁸⁰ Indeed, while the new coalition remains committed to an extended (or 'networked') security concept that includes civilian means, the coalition agreement mainly emphasizes the role of the *Bundeswehr* as 'an essential instrument of German peace policy'.⁸¹ The changing nature of contemporary foreign policymaking and the complex challenges of today's armed conflicts

⁷⁸ Nora Bensahel, 'Organising for Nation Building', *Survival*, Vol.49, No.2, 2007, pp. 43-76, at p. 67.

⁷⁹ The authors would like to thank an anonymous reviewer for this point.

⁸⁰ In general, the term 'civilian conflict prevention' can be found only once in the coalition agreement, referring to the role of the German Federal Police in the field of conflict prevention; see CDU, CSU and FDP, *Wachstum. Bildung. Zusammenhalt. Der Koalitionsvertrag zwischen CDU, CSU und FDP* [Growth. Education. Cohesion. The Coalition Agreement Between CDU, CSU and FDP], Berlin: CDU, 2009, p. 98, accessed at <http://www.cdu.de/doc/pdf/091026-koalitionsvertrag-cducsu-fdp.pdf>.

⁸¹ CDU, CSU and FDP, *Wachstum. Bildung. Zusammenhalt*, pp. 122, 124; our translation.

however demand new instruments precisely like those introduced by the action plan. As long as the Federal Government does not truly commit itself to the implementation of the action plan, however, much time and resources will continue to be wasted at home before actors can even start to address the problems abroad.